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**A Brief Modern, Post-Modern and Contemporary Critical Analysis of
Jürgen Habermas' Theory of Communicative Action.**

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**On Economics and the Circumstances of the Creation of the Euro and
the European Union.**

I

With this analysis, I do not intend to teach the little about economics that I know to anyone - much less to a professor trained in the area -, but it seems pertinent to me, considering the historical and social context in which we are inserted - just as Habermas is and was - to talk a little about money, interest and inflation that are so inherent to contemporary states; in fact, it has been more than two millennia since these principles were applied in states with large market economies. Having said this, I will go on to evaluate in a simple way about inflation - and under the evidence, taken by me as true, that contemporary States, with few exceptions, donate the possibility of the generation of new currencies from 'out of thin air' to central private banks, in which, in general, these same States have expressive participation or ownership of the shares -.

Now, let us imagine an Earth, and that this is the only Earth accessible to a quiet, strange and cunning group of organisms that use language to amorally - if one prefers, instrumentally or objectively - manipulate themselves, whether in speech acts in which they declare truths established or invented by themselves, or when they need to punish those who violate these truths, or when they use lies to achieve their ends. Well, on this Earth there are very few resources and beings, which are limited to 50 males, females, and some offspring of the talking and thinking species; there are 50 fruits that if one were to look at, one would find that they resemble apples on this Earth of ours. There is only one other feature on this strange Earth: golden shells that were left by a now apparently extinct species of organisms. Some males of this group of speaking and thinking organisms decide to use the golden shells as a means of exchange for the fruits, so that a correct distribution according to everyone's needs of possession and consumption of goods is possible, and for a future commercialization of new fruits - produced from the old ones. Initially only 50 golden shells are found. The talking and thinking mathematicians calculate that there is one shell for each apple and one shell for each inhabitant of the strange Earth, they conclude that there is nothing missing and therefore they do not have the need, like us on our Earth, for the concept of inflation. However, after that generation of organisms have started acquiring fruits, some plant them, or divide some among themselves and produce crops. There are now 150 fruits and 75 talking, thinking organisms, but 250 more golden shells have been found by certain astute individuals. These latter individuals decide to create a place to store so many golden shells, and their mathematicians find that each fruit now costs 2 golden shells. Various forms of labor arise over the trade and derivatives of the fruit and fruit trees, but no matter how many more services and jobs and resources are provided, there always seems to be a much more abundant number of shells to be found, so the concept of inflation arises to explain why everything seems to be getting more expensive - and indeed is getting more expensive -. The cunning descendants of the mathematicians and golden shell explorers create the idea that the place of deposit for the golden shells can be an institution for lending golden shells in exchange for goods, such as the homes of other speaking and thinking organisms, or new housing, or for new fruit, or in exchange for services and labor, or in exchange for more golden shells - but everything is mediated through the golden shells - until they find that there are no more golden shells for so many goods. They then create, from the wood and leaves of the fruit trees, a form of paper that has mathematical symbols indicating how much value can be exchanged through this document, and so many more loans are made on the basis of what they declare to be interest in exchange for paper-documents or money or golden shells. Some of the speaking and thinking organisms could no longer pay the interest, lost their property, were imprisoned or enslaved. The rest of this fable does not matter to us...

II

Now, not exactly mixing things up, it is necessary to talk a little about the circumstances of the macroeconomics of the major European states around before the European Union was formed. Germany had certainly learned from the immense economic penalties of the Treaty of Versailles imposed on her after the end of the First World War. In '1913' 4.2 Deutschmarks were worth 1 US dollar, after the end of the war it was worth in mid '1922' 320 Deutschmarks to every US dollar, and very soon after that, thanks to the Treaty, more than a trillion Deutschmarks were worth a single US dollar. You could buy almost nothing with the Deutschmark in those times, not even German products¹, people would get the money and sometimes in winter burn it, because its value was so superfluous that it was better to keep warm than to have it as a means of exchange. Before World War II 2.5 German marks were worth approximately 1 US dollar, at the end of the war 1.1. After WWII the Bundesbank continued its doctrine of low currency production, although increasing inflation considerably more than in the Hitler years. From 1979-1991 Karl Otto Pöhl was president of the Bundesbank and said, "The Bundesbank made the original concept - of the European Monetary System - its leader by making its currency the measure by which other currencies were measured." Since other European countries had a highly inflated currency compared to the Deutschmark, trade in the European zone favored Germany and the debts of France, Italy, England, Spain and other European countries increased, since in the last centuries of European history, states not only incurred debts to finance social, military, structural and economic projects, but incurred debts to pay off more debts, turning debts into unpayable debts², with high and immense profits for bankers and high finance.

The European currencies of the time were exchanged for US dollars, the latter being the only, or one of the last, currencies in the West to be quoted in gold. One U.S. dollar in this period was worth 1/35 of an ounce of gold. European countries traded the injected U.S. dollars into their economies for U.S. gold and thus the U.S. dollar was inflating to the point that the U.S. came close to financial bankruptcy. President Nixon, however, instead of declaring financial bankruptcy, created the petro-dollar to peg the dollar to American oil and allow the Federal Reserve to produce dollars like crazy so that the dollar could continue to be injected into other economies. Inflation in Germany in terms of service and jobs and the country's own currency was much lower than several other European states. What was one of the best currencies on earth between 1955 and 1998 lost

1 **Inflation** <http://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.DEFL.ZS>

<http://www.history.ucsb.edu/faculty/marcuse/projects/currency.htm>

German Consumer Price Index <https://research.stlouisfed.org/fred2/series/DEUCPIALLAINMEI>

2 <https://auditoriacidada.org.br/>

about 73% of its value and it is not surprising that other currencies even more so on the European scene, even before the creation of the euro. Jacques Delors, a French socialist economist and president of the European Commission in January 1985 imagined and took action on the dream of creating a single European currency which would allow European states to create state debt on top of new state debt without the disadvantage of having the Deutschmark preventing intense free usury >>and usury in the illegal sense of the term according to the international code of jurisprudence<<. There were unpopular campaigns in Germany paid for by the German government - one costing 17 million Deutschmarks - to convince the public that the euro would be as stable as the Deutschmark, but statistics show that about 70% of Germans did not favor the idea. And it was known why: the Deutschmark was worth much more than the British pound sterling, the French franc, or the Greek drachma; and tying the German economy to smaller economies would inevitably cause the German economy to decline because of disproportionate debts and exchange rates with these states.

One of the last impulses for the creation of the euro coincided with the fall of the Soviet regime and the fall of the Berlin wall. German Chancellor Helmut Kohl saw the opportunity to reunify Germany at this time, the German constitution guaranteed the unity of Germany as a whole, but in international geopolitical terms it was not that simple. The US, Britain and France still held troops in West Germany and in East Germany the Soviets held forces, so there was no possibility for Germany to reclaim national unity. If Germany reunified it would have the largest European population, a strong industrialized economy, a strong currency stronger than any other European currency and a strategic position in the center of Europe, so what strategic reasons did the US, or France, or Britain or the Soviet Union have to allow the reunification of that country? I would say none. On September 12, 1990 the complete reunification was accomplished according to a series of demands from these countries occupying Germany, which included: payment of 21 billion German marks for the Soviet Union to withdraw its troops from the eastern region; reduced its army and armed forces to less than 370,000 people <<other countries at the time had more than a million soldiers>>, had to renounce the production or possession of nuclear weapons, chemical and biological weapons; no one would be allowed to handle or deploy nuclear weapons in the Berlin area or in East Germany; its forces could only be used in accordance with the UN Charter; and there were agreements that Germany would recognize the full territory of Poland among other neighboring states to avoid future conflict. However, three weeks after the Berlin Wall came down, Helmut Kohl's chief foreign secretary Horst Teltschik noted that "the Federal Government of Germany was now in a delicate strategic position in which it would have to accept any initiative by France on behalf of 'Europe'." Richard von Weizsäcker, former president of West Germany said the following about the euro and that it was: "nothing but the price of reunification." Karl Otto Pöhl, the former president of the Bundesbank said that: "the European monetary union might not have

happened without the reunification of Germany". In other words, Kohl needed to promote the euro in general and the interests of other European states in order for the reunification to be possible - as Mitterrand's advisor Hubert Védrine said at the time -. Jacques Attali, former economic advisor to former president Mitterrand said, "the current currency would not have been realized had it not been for the reservations that Mitterrand had about the reunification of Germany." During Mitterrand's rule in France in the early 1980s, there was a further 30% drop in the franc against the Deutschmark, which was considered embarrassing to Mitterrand and France at the time and was what certainly hurt France's import and export trade, forcing the president to devalue the franc against the Deutschmark even further. Apparently, in a conversation with Margaret Thatcher, Mitterrand said that: "Without a common currency, you and we, are under Germanic domination. When they raise their interest rates, we have to follow them and so do you, even though you do not participate in our monetary system. We can only unite if there is a European Central Bank in which we can decide this together." It is apparently remarkable, too, that officials in the Elysée Palace - President Mitterrand's office - said, "We may have the nuclear weapon, but the Germans have the Deutschmark." The German government itself for a long time had problems with an "anti-inflationary" bank, because, as Maria Lucia Fattorelli >>specialist in public debt and its hearings<< argues, it was not advantageous to either politicians or high finance from an economic point of view. Apparently the German constitution was against the possibility of a non-German currency, but jurists, possibly influenced by politicians, came to the conclusion that it was not unconstitutional, but that if Germany adopted a currency that in the future became unstable, the government could abandon it; however, the constitution was changed so that no dispute about the case in legal terms was possible. In 1992, in the Maastricht Treaty, the euro was definitively established; the European Monetary Institute was founded - a forerunner to the European Central Bank - supposed to guarantee a smooth transition from the Deutschmark to the euro. Countries wanting to join the union had to meet strict conditions of the European Monetary Institute which included having a budget deficit of less than 3% of their GDP and less than 60% domestic debt. It was also stipulated that inflationary prices and long-term interest rates should not be high and stay below certain limits. What I am saying is, as far as I can see, the euro was promised to be as stable as the old Deutschmark, but of course this is not mathematically possible. Italy and Belgium had domestic debts of over 60% when they joined the eurozone, which proves that the exegeses charged are fantasies or lies that are not followed by the Union. The new apparent stabilities caused by the euro would thus allow highly indebted states to be able to pay low interest on their debts without being charged in advance. What happens and has happened at the end of certain crises is that Germany ends up lending money to the most indebted countries itself by running up huge debts and pressuring its own population to pay high taxes, and therefore indebted countries pay less interest to the Union and Germany more interest. So there is

no such thing as economic stability in the Eurozone according to this criticism I am making.

The point of this whole discussion is that, in my opinion, a large part of the reasons why the beloved vision of the European Union - a vision so beloved by Jürgen Habermas, humanists or neo-illuminists, globalists - came to be possible was not really for democratic reasons but for pure economic interest or political influence and manipulation of high finance over the European political class so that a few could enrich themselves at the expense of the labors of the many. This is a bold thesis that is not necessarily stating that these are all or the only reasons why the European Union happened, but it is certainly one of the main ones and it doesn't seem to me to be a democratic decision, but a decision made by political representatives interested in personal profit. So I have my serious doubts about the political propaganda machine that the mainstream media advocates and says and is used by most Europeans today, as if they live in a bed of roses of cultural union and acceptance of differences, welcoming, perhaps boldly, the whole world into the thin arms of Europe - and with not a few social problems -.

A Brief Analysis of Modernity and Post-Modernity, Considering the Work "The Theory of Communicative Action" by Jürgen Habermas.

III

As is known, Habermas wants to realize all his projects of a critical theory of society from German idealism - from Kant to Marx -; this theory makes explicit what "is" can be, given the possibility of what could be. He has as a project of union between philosophy and sociology that is a reconstructive theory, a knowledge about communicative social interests, whether they are theoretical or whether they are intersubjective. Habermas wants to translate German idealism into a fallible language, within the "post-metaphysical" context, with the aim of 'deflating reason', since the philosophies of consciousness and their theories of transcendental statements have completely failed, as have the so-called "first philosophies". Totalizing projects of thought, were what - otherwise - according to the philosopher, led to the cold use of instrumental reason in Auschwitz and that from a dialogical point of view of shared life-worlds, there, in the concentration camps, reason lost part of its credibility as a source of ethical justification, because, in part, it was also the misuse of reason that led to these great disasters. Therefore, the philosopher argues that we should be cautious about having faith in reason as if it were a guarantor of ethical rightness, and this not even if it is a completely "logical" reason.

According to what Habermas interprets from Parsons, through rationality the Life World

takes place. The World of Life is the existential sphere of humans in the world in which there are dialogical interactions between speakers with potential use of reason for them to discuss values, norms of conduct, enjoyments, joys, sorrows, tragedies or emotional needs, bodily needs, to express ideas and feelings and to be heard in these acts by other human beings. Habermas argues that a new constellation for philosophy is the natural sciences; modern philosophy donated meaning to the totality and said the place of the sciences, just like Hegel who spoke of the protozoa and the elliptical orbits of the planets in the solar system and said what science should do, what the arts should do and their places, politics, law and history, among other areas, even theology. This, Habermas tells us, philosophy can no longer do. The great theme of sociology is the transition from community to society and the pathologies that result from this transition. Sociology is born out of the crisis of the Old World - in this case the world in which humans either did not yet have language, or were still largely enchanted by it. I believe, however, that an analysis of some authors of modernity and postmodernity would be helpful in discussing the major obstacles that one could object to Habermasian theory.

IV

Of the issues that dismayed Modernity, the philosophies dealt with issues before the total tyrannical domination of Christian scholastics, but it was after Arthur Schopenhauer that the question of the crisis of humanism became evident. Many would say that Georg Wilhelm Friedrich Hegel was the driving force behind the end of Modernity, creating with his system of the history of consciousness the last great system trying to safeguard in a single system all the supposed truths prior to René Descartes and all the Enlightenment that preceded him. However, I think that Hegel only tried to systematize, or logicize and try to say in totalizing formulas what and in what essentially all those who preceded him were truly conscious; in short, everything that he would interpret and agree with, that is, what they would be conscious of being true. The supposed description of the history of the Absolute Spirit has an undemonstrated premise: that a limited man is certain about the actual history - in which he is present - of the 'Spirit of the World' that he says is his interpretation the history of consciousness. And as far as Hegel is concerned it is that he interprets in universal history 'the universal judgment', taking a motto from Schiller: this is the idea that is proclaimed in the first edition of his *Enzyelopädie der philosophien Wissenschaften im Grundrissen*³, published in Heidelberg in 1817. Hegel believes in the history of humanity's progress as a process of the Absolute Spirit taking "consciousness of freedom", he proclaims that universal history is "the authentic theodicy" the only reason to give meaning to the struggles and conflicts,

³ Hegel, 1956 a, pp. 298-9 (*Enzyelopädie der philosophischen Wissenschaften im Grundrissen, 1817, § 448*).

the “pain” and the “seriousness of the negative” that are proper to the historical process. This reflection within the crisis of Enlightenment humanism only continues the Christian dream of redemption and paradise on earth, but now through secular political-State conflicts. Schopenhauer, on the other hand, will speak of the essence of “divine justice”, which, when clarified, sublimates all false appearances of disharmony and injustice; this being so, he proclaims: “If it were possible to put all the pain of the world on one side of the scale, and all the guilt of the world on the other, the scales would certainly be in equilibrium.”⁴ As is well known, *Die Welt als Wille und Vorstellung* was published one year after the Hegelian *Enzyklopädie* of Heidelberg and states that it is not the universal or world history (*Weltgeschichte*), but the world itself (*Welt*) that is the universal judgment (*Weltgericht*). It is necessary to focus attention on Schopenhauer's important reinterpretation of the word "theodicy" (in Hegel's language) that names it "divine justice", which does not take place in the historical process and in the socio-political changes that the world makes, but is present in the world as it is, without the pretension of remaining at the level of appearances, but of reaching the essence. Schopenhauer, above all, sees in this world pain and suffering as inevitable results of the aims of men's character and the actions of other organisms as the fruit of the essence of the world, namely the will. Friedrich Nietzsche, however as we shall see, treats this supposed "divine justice" with ironic tones, although he drinks in inspiration from it.

V

For Nietzsche, then, the idea had become clear that the “so-called universal history” that he ironizes in his work *Die Geburt der Tragödie aus dem Geiste der Musik* (GT, 7 and 15; I, 56 and 100) and his private correspondence (B, II, 1, p. 190)⁵ had become a “superb metaphor” (CV, 1; I, 759)⁶ and more than “divine justice” what was now generally spoken of was mundane “eternal justice”. This “eternal justice” before whose “court” of the world the Greek state found “justification” despite its “naïve barbarism”, the war, slavery and pain it entailed (CV, 3; I, 771-2)⁷; for him, then, starting with Schopenhauer, among others, the ideal of “universal history” dissipates, the theodicy ends.

4 Nietzsche, *the Aristocratic Rebel*. Schopenhauer, 1976-82 a, pp. 480-4

5 Nietzsche, *the Aristocratic Rebel*. The abbreviations B and CV refer to Friedrich Wilhelm Nietzsche's private correspondences.

6 *Ibid.*

7 *Ibid.*

VI

In place of the theodicy, therefore, there is the cosmodicy, and it is a category that was coined in a letter of 1872 (B, II, 2, pp. 534) by Erwin Rohde, Nietzsche's friend, which was developed by the latter fully in *Die Geburt*. Therefore, one of Schopenhauer's merits to the postmoderns, in my understanding, was to give the conceptual basis for this category in which the nature of all reality is explained and founded on the conflicts between opposites, and that it is war and all real conflicts, in a *sui generis* and comprehensive sense, that form the basis of all that exists and is real. The analysis of the myth of ΠΡΟΜΗΘΕΥΣ (Prometheús) reveals the origin of all conflict in societies in which, on the contrary, the interdependence of the possibility of cultural creation, and therefore of civilization, requires the sacrifice of a social stratum so that the works of aesthetic, physical and exact *epistêmes* are possible; so that then a noble class of men do philosophy, art, science and politics. For a culture to emerge and be magnanimous, worthy of the stages of men's suffering in the world, with great works, there must always, necessarily, be a class of master-self creators, and a class of slaves who are the driving force and the workers of society. On the contrary, the Christian Peccatum Originale, although denied by Hegel as a doctrine that impedes the advance of the consciousness of the Absolute Spirit, is the germ of revolutionary causes, or even, that it is the same as the moralistic revolts to suppose that there is a redemption for all the suffering of these existences either in a world transcendent to this one, or in this one. The germ of the myth of paradise-on-Earth and the overcoming of the 'critique-of-the-valley-of-tears' (as Karl Marx names 'divine-justice') is the hope that history can come to an end in which man's evil existence would finally be corrected, that the world would be corrected, and equality and peace would reign on earth. However, as we can see, this hope is false for Nietzsche, in that 'worldly justice' is eternally the same in every actuality. The 'worldly justice', which men abide by, is always the same, since it is founded, as it were, on sacrifice and war as a broad conflict; this is therefore the 'eternal justice' of all cultures and civilizations. There is, therefore, teleologically no universal High Good that 'must' be fought for in order for history to evolve and tend toward the freedom of all, i.e. to fight against those and their works that are masters-of-themselves.

VII

The solipsistic and pessimistic character is intrinsically subjectivist, and these philosophies that preceded Nietzsche have always pre-supposed, to varying degrees, an internal spiritual essence that would be an 'I in itself' the foundation of reason and all knowledge; that, in short, all post-Cartesian philosophies fall into the same error in having faith in 'consciousness' as the source of discernment of what is 'apparent' or 'essential', or between 'falsehood' or 'truth', or between 'illusory' or 'real'.

Although every Cartesian definition depends closely on “de omnibus dubitandum”, his “universal doubt”, there is a gross error in making factual the existence of an “I” that thinks, a mere little “ego” that would be a prime cause of something “exterior” and, therefore, extensive and proper to accidents. The 'I' as an existent causative essence of the activity of 'thinking' is a postulate and belief in an 'immediate certainty' presupposed as factual; now, that which thinks simply presupposes something that thinks, but not a *subjectum* as a *qualitas occulta* 'causative' of thinking; to presuppose, even, that something existent thinks is already, in itself, a mere supposition, an *ad hoc* hypothesis unproved by thinking. Even if one says “something' thinks, therefore it thinks” - Es denkt, so denkt es - nothing is immediately known or verified beyond thinking. Moreover, that which thinks, tautologically, thinks, therefore, nothing is immediately deduced as existing - this is perhaps, in reality, a postulate impossible to prove - therefore, “consciousness”, “ego” is a mere illusion of grammatical origin which *Jenseits von Gut und Böse* and *Wille zur Macht* correctly concluded.

VIII

For Nietzsche his enemies even became his masters and in the times of the “philosophical workers” like 'Immanuel Kant', 'Hegel' and the neo-Kantians (like Schopenhauer) the deep critical attempt against all philosophy of subjectivity and fundamentalisms, or foundationalisms based on the dichotomies of consciousness (mind-spirit [*Geist*]) and body, and the deep doubt about the naivety of philosophy to want to describe with ultimate objectivity the history of the world is clear. The Schopenhauerian will was perfumed and rationalized so that it was, demonizingly, said to be the character of organisms misrepresenting the objectivity of reason as moral, even as an antithesis of morality. For Nietzsche, on the contrary, morality (a world-distorting reason) is but a mere and desperate consequential form of the will to power of certain men to revile and control aspects of reality - other men - by asserting their supposed moral superiority of self-blame and the guilt of

others. Whereas all *Übermenschen*, the affirmers of the will as it is given to them in their respective projects, designs, and desires, affirm it as an eternal 'yes'; it is for him these men, therefore, the great affirmers of life. The old assumptions conceptualized as 'essence' and 'accident,' 'soul' and 'body,' 'cause' and 'effect,' the subjectivist foundations are liquidated as mere constructs of perspectives that equate different metonomized metaphors - as the concepts are defined by him in *Über Wahrheit und Lüge im außermoralischen Sinne* (1873) -. From the conceptual illusory categorical mesh is derived the eternal anthropocentric delirium of subjugation of nature to man, when the world and not man makes the very destiny of all that exists.

IX

I now return to Habermas and the resulting chapters of "The Theory of Communicative Action" worked on in class. In the first chapter of this book he states that rationality has less to do with the possession of knowledge than with the way in which subjects capable of speaking and acting acquire and employ knowledge. In implicit knowledge we share the World of Life and are rational if we ground our actions, knowledge, possession, etc... For Habermas there are universalizable moral principles such as the democratic Common Good in the Welfare State. The fundamental question Habermas wants us to ask is: How can I say that an inferred action or proposition can be considered rational? This question had apparently also been formulated in "Moral Consciousness and Communicative Action" (1983). He says that a theory of argumentation that aims at logical justifications through the premises with correct deductions and inductions, but considering social intersubjectivity, are possibly rational. According to Habermas, Max Horkheimer critiques capitalism as a radical objectifying or instrumental use of reason. Habermas separates what he determines to be the 'System or the Systems' and the 'Life World or the Life Worlds'; for him it is not that the Systems, such as private banks, money, the state, the law are necessarily against the Life Worlds, but that they have become parasitic on the Life Worlds of certain individuals by committing abuses against them through the misuse of instrumental reason. Some simple examples would be a person who wants to buy the loyalty of a friend in exchange for money or who buys a sexual partner promising him to love him in exchange for influence or money, when clearly these are not due actions as they depend on acts of emotional expressiveness and not material exchange. The 'cognitive content' consists of a) Teleological Action: which is cognitive-instrumental rationality, b) Communicative Action: which is communicative rationality, the objective world of the state of affairs, i.e. the truths or facts, the social world of norms and values, and the subjective world of experiences-verities and which concern speech acts. These three worlds require a discursive rescue, that is, they are dissensual and require argumentation in which the best

argument would be the one in which the deductions or inductions are considered the most convincing or have at least been demonstrated by the claimant or claimants of validity. The 'background knowledge' that Habermas says each individual has - about their Life World - is the Life World itself, in other words, the beginning of everything in an individual's existence is the Life World, consciousness, according to Habermas is only possible dialogically, in the Life World. This is why Habermas disagrees with Marx when the latter created his totalizing theory of the history of capitalism in which economic relations and the work of humans could explain all the evolution and social states of a given historical actuality, when, after the former makes a thorough analysis of Weber's work - among others - it is known that there are many other factors such as religious, cultural, political interactions, etc. that shape the Life World of each individual. The Habermasian point is that the World of Life is given prior to any teleological or instrumental activity and that the value of things or of men does not begin to be established only through work, but that they are given prior through dialogues and the intersubjective relations and use of language of the speakers of a given culture.

X

Here we come to the last part and aim of this paper. Habermas asks us the question if 'it is possible to ask whether certain world images are more rational than others?' His answer, from what I could understand from his work and from the classes I attended on it, seems to be that 'yes'. For him world images refer '...primarily to interpretative systems or cultural world images which mirror the basic knowledge of social groups, as well as ensuring a nexus in the face of the multiplicity of these groups' orientations to action'. According to Habermas, there are three stages of world image from a historical point of view, namely: 1st) Mythical Image, which would correspond to the primitive Neolithic world until the invention of writing - as far as I could understand -, 2nd) Metaphysical Image, which would go through the Greek and Latin polytheistic world images and the transition to Christianity and 3rd) Modern World Image, which would see the emergence of capitalism, natural law and modern law. The mythical image or the primitive myth is still partially linked to nature, because it does not distinguish between society and its links with it; this is because the productive forces (ciences and techniques) have not developed to the point of giving some control against the adversities of the weather and natural forces that endanger humans. Already for the "Modern" world rationality is measured in the dissensus or dissonance between world images and how willing or open individuals are to argue for their beliefs and contents of truth or their claims of truth or validity. Now, having said that, I ask myself: why does Habermas have preferences for world images? The fundamental question does not infer that there must be the most

rational world image that can exist... In other words, 'is there the most rational of all world images?' Now, from a logical point of view, the argumentation of Carl Schmitt's defence of Hitler - to be the future Führer of the Reich - is rather well justified according to his premises in his arguments and theses; he makes correct and strong deductions - I am not saying he was right, I am saying he validated his arguments from a logical or rational point of view -. As much as Habermas these days abhors Carl Schmitt and the National Socialists, one cannot say with absolute certainty that totalitarian theories, such as Nazism, or Communism, or a theory about Monarchy, Biarchy - as was the case in Sparta -, or an Aristocracy, or anarcho-capitalist libertarianism, or any non-democratic system, they are less rational or less justifiable than democracy. As I exemplified at the beginning of the paper, the European Union itself has several flaws in its own formation, however much the hopes of humanists see it as a bulwark of democracy, there is nothing beforehand that demonstrates democracy as the ideal of modern or contemporary governments. In my understanding this answer is irresolvable - or can be an insurmountable obstacle - in the Habermasian system, even if he appeals to other concepts of emancipation and discourses against the pathologies of the system, for it is always possible even rationally, or logically, to justify arguments against the emancipation of the majority, and it is not always the case that the emancipation of a minority or a majority will always lead to a desirable, or better, or to more 'benevolent' ends, whatever our definitions and beliefs of 'good' and 'evil' may be.